

Robust Wind Farm Optimization Using Monte Carlo Methods

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Abstract

Wake effects significantly minimize the power production of downstream turbines in wind farms. Thus yaw control is employed to increase power gains. Strategically placing turbines within specified bounds has as well been observed to affect the power output of wind farms. There is however sufficient empirical evidence that proves that aerodynamic variables such as wind direction and speed are characterized by much uncertainty. In order to develop more robust models for wind farm energy production the aforementioned variables of interest must be properly described to present a more realistic situation. This work focuses on the quantification of uncertainties associated with yaw orientation, and turbine placement in wind farm annual energy production (AEP) optimization with Monte Carlo Methods. An understanding, and proper treatment of these uncertainties will greatly aid in improving the accuracy of wind farm annual power output predictions.

Introduction

Wind turbines grouped in large farms can produce significant effects on each other through wake deficits, which can result in up to 40% power reduction [1]. When the turbine yaw angles, and positions are set, wake effects on downstream turbines changes with variations in wind direction and speed. Finding the optimum yaw angle of all the turbines in a farm with only the average wind direction and speed can thus result in significant power-production losses as wind flow is naturally stochastic. To maximize gains, optimal layouts and yaw orientations must be obtained with considerations of the associated uncertainty in wind direction and speed.

As a first step, we seek to create a model for wind farm AEP prediction deterministically considering yaw as the design variable. Yaw is dependent on the direction of incoming wind, and wake effects. The total power generated in a wind farm for a given direction is given by

$$P = \sum_{i=1}^{nturbs} P_i$$

with

$$P_i = \frac{1}{2} C_p A_i U_i^3$$

Where $nturbs$ is the number of wind turbines in a farm, C_p is the power coefficient, A_i is the rotor swept area, and U_i the effective hub velocity for each turbine. The amount of energy converted from the wind into electrical energy by a wind farm is primarily dependent on the wind speed, and the wind speed is greatly reduced in wake regions, designing a wind farm's layout and yaw control method to minimize wake effects is therefore crucial [6]. The Flow Redirection and Induction in Steady-state (FLORIS) wake model is used in this work to estimate the wake effects and calculate the effective hub velocities [4]. The FLORIS model is a derivative of the Jensen wake deficit model and the wake deflection model presented in [4]. The FLORIS model builds on the Jensen model by defining three separate wake zones with differing expansion and decay rates to more accurately describe the velocity deficit across the wake region. A simple overlap ratio of the area of the rotor in each zone of each shadowing wake to the full rotor area is used to determine the effective hub velocity of a given turbine. A simple overview of the FLORIS model, showing the zones and overlap areas, is shown in Figure 1.1. The model has three zones with varying diameters that depend on tuning parameters.

Figure 1.1 The FLORIS Wake Model showing the three zones with varying diameters, $D_{w,q}$ that depend on tuning parameters k_e and $m_{e,q}$. (image taken from [4])

The effective hub velocity is computed using the overlap ratio, A_q^{OL} of the total rotor-swept area to the part of the rotor-swept area overlapping each wake zone respectively. Further details of this can be found in [6].

The AEP is then estimated using

$$AEP = \frac{hr}{yr} \sum_i^{nturbs} P_i f_i$$

Where hr/yr is the number of hours in a year, and f_i is the frequency of wind from a given direction.

Optimization Problem:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Maximize: } AEP \\
& \text{Design Variables: } x_i, y_i, \text{ wind direction} \\
& \text{subject to : } S_{ij} \geq 2D \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 60 \quad i \neq j \\
& \quad \quad \quad -30^\circ \leq yaw_i \leq 30^\circ
\end{aligned}$$

where S_{ij} is the distance between each pair of turbines i and j . We have as well set the yaw the maximum and minimum yaw angles to 30° and -30° respectively, and confined the turbines to specified bounds in our optimizations.

Methodology

Although methods such as Polynomial Chaos Expansion, and Universal Kriging have been proven to produce significantly higher performance [2], Monte Carlo simulations remain a simple and effective forward propagation tool for treating uncertainties in the wind farm layout optimization process. As such random sampling routines will be embedded in an optimization algorithm to reveal the possible outcomes of power production under uncertain conditions. The algorithm is easy to parallelize, allowing for completely independent function evaluations [3].

The Monte Carlo method uses a random sample set based off a desired distribution and evaluates the objective function over the sample set. The mean value of the set of outputs generated from the samples becomes the objective value to be optimized. For our model we considered three cases of 4 x 4 grid layout with standard deviations of 2, 5, and 10 degrees to generate the sample of uncertain wind directions (see figure below for the case with 2 standard deviations). The optimized yaw angles, and x and y positions then represent the orientations that produces the highest AEP given the fact that the wind will be changing direction occasionally with the frequency outlined in the sample distribution.

Figure 1.2 Sample distribution used to calculate objective value under uncertainty

Surrogate Model Method

One of the methods we sought to use was creating a surrogate model that includes the uncertainty and using that model for the optimization. The FLORIS model itself is able to evaluate relatively quickly, but the large sample size for uncertainty wind directions becomes expensive for each function evaluation during the optimization. The idea behind using the surrogate is to evaluate the function under uncertainty over a specific sample size to determine the model weights. Once those weights have been determined, the optimization becomes much faster. In theory, the weights can be determined using a supercomputer running the samples in parallel, and then multiple optimizations can be run on a desktop computer using various starting points and holding certain design variables constant to see how the optimal solution changes.

We began developing the model using polynomials as the basis functions because of the simplicity of the implementation. Further testing should be done to find a best fitting set of basis functions with the least amount of terms. For polynomials, the number of terms increases exponentially based on the number of dimensions. For the Amalia wind farm there are 60 turbines, each of which we want to control yaw angle, x position, and y position. This is a total of 180 variables, which for a 6th order polynomial produces over 53 billion terms. We were only able to obtain values for up to a 5th order polynomial. The model error was computed using a 70:30 training to testing ratio from 1000 sample points. The model average % error and the required number of terms as the polynomial order increases is shown in the plot below.

Figure 1.3 Percent error (left axis) and number of terms (right axis) as the polynomial order increases

We chose to test the quadratic model because it had the lowest error of the polynomials we were able to test and also because it would have the quickest computation time. The results from the surrogate were not too impressive. For the single wind direction changing only yaw angles the output favored the boundaries. All of the turbines were yawed at either -30 or 30 degrees. When adding in the position as a design variable, the turbines gravitated toward the boundaries (for this case x: 4000m, y: 5000m) and the yaw angles did not change. This may be a result from the polynomial order being far too small to fully characterize the large amount of design variables.

Figure 1.4 Results using the surrogate model for one wind direction with only yaw control (left) and the full wind rose with yaw and position control (right)

Results

So far we have run optimizations using both a deterministic approach and the Monte Carlo uncertainty method. We used the Floris model with the Amalia wind farm layout to test our method. Table 1 lists the flow and turbine parameters we used for this optimization.

Wind Speed	8 m/s
1 Wind Direction	0°
Wind Frequency	1
Air Density, ρ	1.1716 kg/m ³
5 MW Turbines	60
Turbine Efficiency	1
Rotor Diameter, D	126.4 m
C_p	0.4585

Table 1: Parameters used in the Floris Model for the Amalia wind farm

We used the python optimizer SNOPT with the pyOpt package to optimize our function. SNOPT is a gradient based optimizer. We did not provide analytic gradients and simply used the built-in finite differencing method with a step size of $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$. The optimized turbine layouts are shown below.

Figure 2: Plot of deterministic solution yaw angles

Figure 3: Plot of uncertainty solution yaw angles

Table 2: Comparison of yaw solutions when solved using deterministic and uncertainty methods

	Deterministic AEP (GWh)	Expected AEP (GWh)
Deterministic Solution	885.96	863.46
Uncertainty Solution	886.01	863.72

Interestingly, the solution obtained by optimizing with uncertainty shows better results when evaluated using both deterministic and uncertain methods. In theory the deterministic solution should produce better results for a deterministic evaluation. This suggests that we need to tune the optimization setup more for the final product.

We plan to move forward with making adjustments in scaling the model properly for better results and attempting to obtain analytic gradients or find the optimal finite differencing technique for our scenario.

The results showing a comparison between the deterministic solutions for a 4x4 grid of turbines compared against the optimizations considering uncertainty with different standard deviations. Even for the deterministic model the optimization under uncertainty performs better, which should not be the case. For these results we used a sample size of 10,000 points to generate the uncertainty distribution. We believe that our model may need a greater number of samples to produce more accurate results.

Table 2: Results comparing deterministic solution against solutions for 2, 5, 10 standard deviations. All values are in kWh.

$\sigma = 2$ deg	Deterministic AEP	Expected
Deterministic Sol:	136203561.1	79261383.94
OUU sol:	138570997.9	111606175.4

$\sigma = 5$ deg	Deterministic AEP	Expected
Deterministic Sol:	136203561.1	79261216.71
OUU sol:	152602236.6	112815069.7

$\sigma = 10$ deg	Deterministic AEP	Expected
Deterministic Sol:	136203561.1	79261207.91
OUU sol:	168766161.5	143930010.9

Conclusions

It is clear from both results studies that our OOU solution always outperforms the deterministic computations. This is however contrary to what we observe from the work of [4]. We believe that a larger sample size will produce results consistent with current research. A close inspection of our computational model will also reveal further flaws in our model.

Using Monte Carlo methods is computationally expensive, but the tradeoff is that it is easy to implement. Another benefit is that it is a ‘black box’ method, so it can be used without having to make any alterations to the code created for the model. Considering uncertainty in optimizing yaw angle consistently produced higher results when calculating the average power over the normal distribution of wind directions.

References

1. Sanderse B, van der Pijl SP, Koren B. “Review of computational fluid dynamics for wind turbine wake aerodynamics.” *Wind Energy*. 2011. **14**:799-819
2. David Matthäus, Pietro Bortolotti, Jaikumar Loganathan, and Carlo L. Bottasso. "Propagation of Uncertainties Through Wind Turbine Models for Robust Design Optimization", 35th Wind Energy Symposium, AIAA SciTech Forum, (AIAA 20171849) <http://dx.doi.org/10.2514/6.2017-1849>
3. J. R. A. Martins, Ning, J. Hicken . Multidisciplinary Design Optimization
4. A. S. Padrón, A. P J Stanley, J. J. Thomas, J. J. Alonso, and A. Ning. "Polynomial chaos for the computation of annual energy production in wind farm layout optimization." *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 753 (2016): 032021 (in review).
<http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/753/3/032021>
5. P. Fleming, A. Ning, P. Gebraad and K. Dykes 2016 “Wind plant system engineering through optimization of layout and yaw control *Wind Energy*” 19 329–344
6. Thomas, J., Gebraad, P., and Ning, A., “Improving the FLORIS Wind Plant Model for Compatibility with Gradient-based Optimization,” *Wind Engineering*, May 2016, (in review)